

RANS-VOF modelling of the hydraulic performance of the LOWREB caisson

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Abstract

The LOWREB caisson is an innovative multi-chambered, low-reflection structure that incorporates inner weirs at each dissipative chamber to promote wave energy dissipation. It was designed to be applied either as external caisson breakwater or as low reflection quay-wall. In this paper, the OpenFOAM® CFD numerical package was used to implement a RANS-VOF numerical model of the LOWREB caisson concept, which was then validated using results from experimental tests in a two-step approach: qualitatively, by comparing the “wave-structure” interaction on both physical and numerical models, and quantitatively, by comparing the reflection coefficients determined from the results of the numerical model simulations and those from the physical model tests. Once validated, the numerical model was used to carry out a comprehensive study of the hydrodynamic behavior of the LOWREB caisson aiming the understanding of the wave energy dissipation mechanisms and the assessment of its hydraulic efficiency with respect to wave reflection under an extended range of hydrodynamic conditions (*e.g.*, water levels, wave heights, and wave periods). The numerical study confirmed the importance of the inner weirs on the wave energy dissipation. The hydraulic efficiency of the LOWREB caisson was found to be highly influenced by the combined effect of the wave period and water level. However, the influence of the wave height is not negligible: in general, energy dissipation increases with the wave height. Overall, the LOWREB caisson presents its best performance for the high and mean water level conditions, with all the values of the reflection coefficient below 70% and most of them in the range 30%-60%. The worse results obtained for the lower water level were attributed to the difficulties that waves have to overtop the weirs and enter the dissipative chambers, for this water level. In addition, streamlines, velocity and vorticity fields enabled obtaining important insights on the wave energy dissipation processes that take place during the wave-structure interaction, which results in the development of several vortices, not only inside the dissipative chambers, but also in front of the structure.

Keywords

wave reflection; low-reflection structure; wave-structure interaction; LOWREB; numerical modelling; OpenFOAM

1. Introduction

Sea ports should provide shelter and quiet conditions for the safe berthing and mooring of ships, as well as to enable an efficient handling of cargos. In a first instance, those conditions are ensured by breakwaters, which prevent sea wave propagation into the inner harbour basins and may also promote the dissipation of its energy (Rosa-Santos and Taveira-Pinto, 2013). Inside the harbour basin, additional wave energy dissipation may occur if low reflective solutions are chosen for the port terminals and other internal boundaries (Taveira-Pinto *et al.*, 2011). Soft countermeasures, such as tension mooring (Rosa-Santos *et al.*, 2014), may also be used to reduce downtime and avoid mooring problems at ocean facing ports, which are often related with excessive motions of

40 the moored ships caused directly by wave action or indirectly by wave related phenomena (López and Iglesias,
41 2014; López *et al.*, 2015), namely wave reflection.

42 Rubble-mound structures have good wave dissipation characteristics, but sometimes are an infeasible option due
43 to economical or technical constrains. In this case, perforated-wall caisson breakwaters may be used to avoid the
44 drawbacks of the traditional vertical breakwaters (Suh *et al.*, 2006), which have a high reflective behaviour,
45 ensuring better ship navigation and manoeuvring conditions in its vicinity and also lower wave disturbance in the
46 internal harbour basins.

47 Jarlan (1961) proposed the first concept of a perforated caisson breakwater: it consists of a perforated front wall,
48 a solid back wall and one wave-dissipating chamber between them. After that pioneering work, modifications to
49 the so-called Jarlan type breakwater have been proposed and studied, for instance including two (Li *et al.*, 2003)
50 or multiple (Huang, 2006) wave-dissipating chambers, internal horizontal perforated plates (Yip and Chwang,
51 2000; Hu *et al.*, 2002), slightly inclined porous plates (Cho and Kim, 2008), as well as internal wave-dissipating
52 chambers partially or completely filled with rocks of one (Isaacson *et al.*, 2000) or two different gradings (Liu *et al.*,
53 2007). Less conventional alternatives were also studied, as the concentric two-cylinder structures composed
54 of an internal impermeable cylinder and an external thin and porous wall (Song and Tao, 2007). These solutions
55 reduce both the transmitted and the reflected wave energy as well as the hydrodynamic loading on the structure.
56 In fact, the incident wave energy is partly reflected at the perforated seaward wall and partly transmitted through
57 the openings to the wave-dissipating chambers, in which energy dissipation occurs due to resonance phenomena,
58 vortices and friction losses. Those physical processes are governed mainly by the porosity of the perforated wall
59 and by the wave chamber width.

60 In order to reduce the wave disturbance within the port, several dissipative (or anti-reflective) concrete blocks
61 were also developed for berthing structures and harbour basin slopes: Igloo blocks (Bottin, 1976), WAROK
62 blocks (Ijima *et al.*, 1976), BARRA blocks (Berenguer and Arana, 2002), NOREF blocks (Taveira-Pinto *et al.*,
63 2011), among others. As their counterparts designed for applications in breakwaters, the structures built with
64 those blocks absorb a fraction of the incident wave energy by turbulence, viscous friction and resonance. In
65 addition, non-conventional and traditional designs of wave absorbing quay-walls, consisting of a single partial
66 wave chamber, with limited height and depth above and below the water level, filled with natural stones placed
67 to form a rubble mound with a certain slope and porosity, were also proposed and studied (Theocharis *et al.*,
68 2011; Altomare and Gironella, 2014). Huang *et al.* (2011) presents a comprehensive review on the hydraulic
69 performance and wave loadings of perforated and slotted coastal structures.

70 Many of the low reflection concepts initially developed for breakwaters can also be adapted and applied in port
71 terminals (*e.g.* Liu and Faraci, 2014). The adaptations are essentially motivated by the different functions of the
72 structures, local water depths and wave conditions. In fact, the external breakwaters are exposed to unhindered
73 extreme waves, whereas nearby the port terminals smaller waves are expected, since only a fraction of the wave
74 energy can enter the port and the waves generated locally by wind and passing ships are small both in terms of
75 height and period.

76 Pinto (2012) proposed a new concept of a low reflection structure, the LOWREB caisson, which is suitable for
77 both applications, external caisson breakwaters and inner low reflective quay-walls, that is composed of one or
78 more dissipative wave chambers, with varying bottom elevations and widths, separated by perforated-walls with
79 pre-defined porosities. The main innovation in the LOWREB caisson are the inner weirs located at each
80 dissipative chamber. The experimental proof of concept of this novel caisson showed that it is a valid concept for

81 marine applications, namely harbour breakwaters and quay-walls, because of its wave energy dissipation
82 capacity, for which the inner weirs were found to play a major role (Ciocan *et al.*, 2017).

83 Physical modelling is a valuable and reliable tool to evaluate the effectiveness of low reflection structures, being
84 widely applied in the proof of concept testing of new concepts (*e.g.*, Taveira-Pinto *et al.*, 2011; Theocharis *et al.*,
85 2011). However, since experimental studies are often expensive and time-consuming, the characterization of the
86 reflection characteristics of the structures is carried out only for a limited number of wave conditions and setups.
87 Therefore, the simulation of the interactions between the incident waves and the low reflection structures is also
88 important for a detailed characterization of their hydraulic efficiency with regard to wave reflection, and a more
89 comprehensive understanding of the wave energy dissipation mechanisms.

90 In this respect, different mathematical and numerical approaches have been developed and successfully validated
91 with experimental data, namely: analytical and semi-analytical methods based on potential flow theory (*e.g.*, Liu
92 *et al.*, 2007; Liu *et al.*, 2008), semi-empirical methods based on multi-parametric nonlinear regression tools (*e.g.*,
93 Garrido and Medina, 2012), computational fluid dynamic (CFD) models (Lee *et al.*, 2017), among others.
94 However, since viscous effects of boundary layer separation, turbulence, wave breaking and overtopping are
95 important in this kind of applications (Fugazza and Natale, 1992; Ciocan *et al.*, 2017), CFD models based on the
96 Navier Stokes equations are, in principle, more appropriate for the simulation of wave-structure interactions, by
97 accounting the most relevant physical phenomena affecting the dissipation of wave energy.

98 The application of the Reynolds–Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) equations to model wave-structure
99 interactions has evolved significantly in the last decades, being now possible to study perforated and permeable
100 structures at reasonable level of detail and accuracy, with only a few simplifications in the translation of the
101 problem physics. In fact, the range of application of such models is very wide, extending from the traditional
102 coastal engineering problems (Higuera *et al.*, 2013) to the development and optimization of marine renewable
103 energy technologies (Lopez *et al.*, 2014). In addition, RANS models have already been successfully validated for
104 the simulation of several complex hydrodynamic phenomena in the coastal and port engineering fields. Their
105 principal drawback is the high computational power required.

106 Presently, RANS models are able to realistically generate ocean waves and also integrate active wave absorption
107 methods (*e.g.*, del Jesus *et al.*, 2012; Higuera *et al.*, 2015; Vanneste and Troch, 2015). Physical phenomena such
108 as wave breaking, run up, run down, bottom friction, wave interaction with porous structures, wave overtopping,
109 and wave energy dissipation are also reproduced with a satisfactory level of detail and accuracy (*e.g.*, Lara *et al.*,
110 2012; Higuera *et al.* 2014a; Jensen *et al.*, 2014; Wu *et al.*, 2014), making possible their application in practical
111 coastal engineering problems (*e.g.*, Higuera *et al.*, 2014b). One of the greatest advantages of the CFD models is
112 their intrinsic ability of providing pressure and velocity profiles in different locations of the structure, allowing a
113 more comprehensive understanding of the problem physics, still with a high level of fidelity and still relatively
114 time-efficient when compared to physical model testing.

115 In this paper, the CFD code OpenFOAM® is used to study the interaction of waves with the LOWREB caisson,
116 in order to better characterize its hydrodynamic response with regard to wave reflection for a wide range of test
117 conditions, covering typical applications of this novel caisson in breakwaters and quay-walls. The results of the
118 experimental proof of concept tests (Ciocan *et al.*, 2017) are used in the validation of the numerical model. The
119 numerical simulations are also explored to gain a more comprehensive insight into the wave energy dissipation
120 mechanisms of this caisson concept, looking at its future optimization.

121 This paper is structured as follows. The LOWREB caisson concept is briefly described in Section 2, together
122 with the main conclusions of the previous experimental proof of concept tests. The numerical approach applied
123 and the testing programme is presented in Section 3. Then, Section 4 describes the validation of the numerical
124 model as well as the novel insights on the hydrodynamic performance of the LOWREB caisson. The validated
125 numerical model is applied to characterize the performance of the structure for the new hydrodynamic conditions
126 and the results are discussed. Finally, the summary and conclusions are given in Section 5.

127 2. The LOWREB caisson

128 The LOWREB caisson is composed of one or more dissipative chambers with varying bottom elevations (and
129 widths), separated by perforated-walls with pre-defined porosities, similarly to other low reflection structures.
130 The main innovation in this concept is the inner weirs, located at the beginning of each dissipative chamber,
131 Figure 1, which introduce additional dissipation mechanisms. The shape of the weirs was designed to favour
132 water movement in the rear wall direction, reducing wave reflection. The return flow over the weirs falls in the
133 water nappe created by the lower weir and so on, creating a succession of free falling nappes at each weir edge.
134 This process generates intense turbulence, flow aeration and, therefore, energy dissipation (Ciocan *et al.*, 2016).

135
136

Figure 1 – LOWREB caisson: 3D perspectives.

137 The height of the successive LOWREB chambers reduces in the rearward direction to materialize the “cascade”
138 of weirs and to improve the overall stability of the structure, due to the extra weight added to the lower part of
139 the caisson. The space behind each weir (i.e., below its crest level, Figure 1) can be filled with rubble to improve
140 energy dissipation and to increase the stability of the caisson. The LOWREB concept was developed to be used
141 in external caisson breakwaters or inner low reflective quay-walls (Ciocan *et al.*, 2016).

142 Owing to the complexity of the LOWREB geometry and the hydraulic processes associated to the wave-structure
143 interaction, there are no general design criteria to be followed. Hence, the preliminary design of this caisson was
144 based on existing knowledge about low reflection, perforated structures (*e.g.*, Williams *et al.*, 2000; Bergmann
145 and Oumeraci, 2001; Chen *et al.*, 2002; Li *et al.*, 2003; Huang, 2006). For example, for increased energy
146 dissipation, a perforated and multi-chambered caisson was proposed, with the porosities of the perforated-walls
147 decreasing gradually along the incident wave direction.

148 A LOWREB caisson consisting on a three-chamber, perforated-wall structure with inner weirs was tested in the
 149 wave basin of the Hydraulics Laboratory of the Hydraulics, Water Resources and Environment Division of the
 150 Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, Portugal. This proof of concept study aimed at confirming the
 151 initial design of the LOWREB caisson, by assessing the impact of the inner weirs on wave energy dissipation
 152 and by evaluating the efficiency of this new caisson in the reduction of the reflected wave energy. Hence, three
 153 physical models with the same overall geometry and dimensions but different wall porosities and vertical slots'
 154 arrangements were built on a geometrical scale of 1:50 and tested under the same hydrodynamic conditions to
 155 study how these affect the LOWREB performance. The experimental tests covered only two water levels and a
 156 limited number of wave conditions.

157 The experimental study confirmed that the LOWREB caisson is a valid concept for harbour structures, due to its
 158 wave energy dissipation capacity, for which the inner weirs were found to play a major role. In fact, the variation
 159 of the reflection coefficient between the three tested models with varying porosity was negligible being this
 160 result attributed to the very large porosities considered in the study (67 and 80%). The obtained results suggest
 161 that the perforated structures considered were transparent to the incident waves and that the wave energy
 162 dissipation was, essentially, governed by the inner weirs, which induce vortexes, air entrainment and intense
 163 turbulence, therefore confirming the innovative character of the LOWREB caisson (Ciocan *et al.*, 2016).

164 The experimental results also indicate that the hydraulic efficiency of the LOWREB caisson increases with the
 165 wave height for the lower water level and with the wave period for the highest. Greater efficiency with respect to
 166 wave reflection was accomplished for the highest water level. For the lower water level, the LOWREB caisson
 167 roughly performed as an impervious structure for the waves with the smaller heights.

168 Since the importance of the inner weirs was clearly demonstrated experimentally, it is now of interest to obtain
 169 more insight about the wave energy dissipation processes directly related to those elements (*i.e.*, the innovative
 170 part of the LOWREB caisson), and to assess the LOWREB hydraulic efficiency with respect to wave reflection
 171 for an extended range of hydrodynamic conditions, including applications, not only as external breakwater, but
 172 also as a low-reflection inner quay-wall.

173 3. Materials and methods

174 3.1. Numerical model

175 As aforementioned, the numerical study of the LOWREB caisson was carried out by means of the open-source
 176 CFD package OpenFOAM® v4.1, a set of C++ libraries to solve complex problems, among them fluid flows and
 177 turbulence, using finite volume discretization (OpenFOAM®). Moreover, the OpenFOAM® package includes
 178 mesh generation tools and pre- and post-processing utilities.

179 The calculations were performed by using the *interFoam* solver, which solves the Reynolds Averaged Navier–
 180 Stokes (RANS) equations for two incompressible phases. The RANS equations describe the motion of a fluid by
 181 the mass conservation (Eq.1) and momentum conservation (Eq.2) equations:

$$182 \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0 \quad , \quad (1)$$

$$183 \quad \frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{U} \mathbf{U}) - \nabla \cdot (\mu_{eff} \nabla \mathbf{U}) = -\nabla p^* - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{x} \nabla \rho + \nabla \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mu_{eff} \quad , \quad (2)$$

184 where \mathbf{U} is the fluid velocity vector, ρ is the fluid density, p^* is the pseudo-dynamic pressure, \mathbf{g} is the
 185 acceleration of gravity, \mathbf{x} is the position vector, and μ_{eff} is the effective dynamic viscosity, which considers the

186 molecular dynamic viscosity plus the turbulent viscosity given by the turbulence model. In this study, the
 187 turbulence model selected was the renormalization group (RNG) $k-\varepsilon$ model (Yakhot *et al.*, 1992). The RNG $k-\varepsilon$
 188 model attempts to address some of the weaknesses of the standard $k-\varepsilon$ model by accounting for the contribution
 189 of smaller scales of motion, and it was already used successfully for solving similar coastal engineering
 190 problems (*e.g.*, Lin *et al.*, 2017).

191 The volume of fluid (VOF) method (Hirt and Nichols, 1981) was used for tracking of the water free surface. In
 192 this method, a phase function (α) indicates the quantity of water per unit volume at each cell. Therefore, when a
 193 cell is full of water, the value of the volume fraction function is $\alpha = 1$; when the cell is empty of water (full of
 194 air), it is $\alpha = 0$; and when the interface cuts the cell, the function takes a value between 0 and 1. In OpenFOAM®
 195 the volume fraction is solved by an advection equation:

$$196 \quad \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{U}\alpha) + \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{U}_c \alpha (1 - \alpha)] = 0, \quad (3)$$

197 where \mathbf{U}_c is the artificial compressive velocity which contributes to limit the smearing of the interface.

198 The pressure-velocity coupling is solved using the PIMPLE algorithm: a combination of PISO (pressure implicit
 199 with splitting of operators) and SIMPLE (semi-implicit method for pressure-linked equations) algorithms. A
 200 detailed explanation of these algorithms can be found in Jasak (1996).

201 For wave generation and absorption, the *waves2Foam* open-source toolbox (Jacobsen *et al.*, 2012) was used.
 202 This toolbox allows the generation of regular waves of different theories including, among others, Stokes first,
 203 second and fifth order, as well as irregular waves. Regarding the absorption of reflected waves, *waves2Foam*
 204 incorporates the relaxation zone technique. In this method, the fluid velocity and the volume fraction are relaxed
 205 at every time step towards target values, following:

$$206 \quad \phi = \alpha_R \phi_{\text{computed}} + (1 - \alpha_R) \phi_{\text{target}} \quad (4)$$

207 where ϕ can be either \mathbf{U} or α , and α_R is the relaxation function formulated as follows:

$$208 \quad \alpha_R(\chi_R) = 1 - \frac{\exp(\chi_R^{3.5}) - 1}{\exp(1) - 1} \quad \text{for } \chi_R \in [0, 1], \quad (5)$$

209 being χ_R the length scale along the relaxation zone. Thus, the relaxation function decreases from 1 at the
 210 beginning of the relaxation zone, to 0 at the end of this zone. In order to prevent any wave reflection, the
 211 relaxation zone should be sufficiently long.

212 For all the simulations ran, the time step was automatically controlled and adjusted at each iteration by the
 213 Courant number (C) in such a way that $C \leq 0.25$, ensuring numerical stability. This methodology led to time
 214 steps around 10^{-4} s.

215 3.2. Computational domain and boundary conditions

216 The computational domain is a reproduction of the experimental set-up (Ciocan *et al.*, 2017): a wave flume with
 217 a small-scale LOWREB model (1:50) located at the end (Figure 2). Two main differences should be pointed out.
 218 First, the width of the numerical wave flume was reduced to one cell. Second, its effective length was reduced
 219 compared with that of the experimental configuration, intending to diminish the computational cost of the tests.
 220 In any case, the length of the numerical flume allows, for all the wave conditions tested, the development of, at
 221 least, two wave lengths between the generation zone and the LOWREB model. Figure 2 also shows the location

222 of the wave gauges (WG) and the extreme water levels studied: High Water Level (HWL) and Low Water Level
223 (LWL).

224

225

Figure 2. Sketch of the computational domain (not to scale) and detail of the LOWREB model.

226 Since the LOWREB structure is located at the end of the numerical wave flume and there is no wave
227 transmission beyond it, the outlet relaxation zone was disregarded. Thus, the inlet relaxation zone was the only
228 one implemented (Figure 2). Taking into account that all the energy not dissipated in the LOWREB is reflected
229 towards the inlet boundary of the numerical wave flume, the length of the relaxation zone was set equal to two
230 wavelengths, a length that ensures a correct dissipation even for great amounts of reflected energy (e.g., Hu *et*
231 *al.*, 2016).

232 The still water level was set up at a y -coordinate equal to 0. Thus, those cells with a negative y -coordinate were
233 filled with water, i.e., volume fraction α equal to 1, and those cells with a positive y -coordinate were filled with
234 air, i.e., volume fraction α equal to 0. The elevations of the free surface were measured at three positions in front
235 of the structure (Figure 2), preserving the spacing between them used in the experimental tests.

236 The computational domain was discretized using the OpenFOAM® mesh generation tool *snappyHexMesh*, an
237 algorithm that refines the mesh and adjusts it to fit around a provided geometry using quadratic refinement.
238 Three different regions can be distinguished in the mesh (Figure 3). The first one, the greater, goes from the inlet
239 to the beginning of the transition zone. In this section, a uniform mesh along the x -axis was established. The cell
240 size was determined according to the wavelength in such a way that, at least, there were 50 cells per wavelength
241 (Vanneste and Troch, 2015). Along the y -axis, a non-uniform mesh was established, with a finer sub-mesh
242 region around the free surface, where a cell size of $\Delta y = 5$ mm was implemented. It implies a $H/\Delta y$ ratio greater
243 than 20 for the largest tested waves and greater than or equal to 2 for the smallest ones, which was found to be
244 sufficient in similar applications (Vanneste and Troch, 2015). For the first eight layers of cells near the free
245 surface (both above and below) a cell size of $\Delta y = 10$ mm was set. Finally, a cell size of $\Delta y = 20$ mm was used
246 for the remaining cells of this region.

247 The second section is the transition zone. It follows the same discretization of the previous section in the y -axis.
 248 However, along the x -axis a variable cell size was established, using a growth rate in which the cell size was
 249 reduced slowly providing a smooth transition from the cell size in the propagation section to that in the model
 250 section. Finally, the third section of the computational domain is the model testing zone. In this zone, a base cell
 251 size of $\Delta x = \Delta y = 20$ mm was used. The cells near the walls of the LOWREB model were refined to easily
 252 accommodate the shape of the model. Three levels of refinement and two buffer layers were used in order to
 253 achieve a smooth transition between cell sizes. In addition, a refinement box was used both in front and inside
 254 the LOWREB model to reduce the cell size to $\Delta x = \Delta z = 5$ mm, which was shown to provide enough detail (e.g.,
 255 Higuera *et al.*, 2014b). All the cells in this section have an aspect ratio of 1, which was shown to be the best for
 256 solving wave breaking (Jacobsen *et al.*, 2012). To achieve a two-dimensional domain, one cell was established in
 257 the z direction in the whole domain.

258
 259 **Figure 3. (a) Sketch of the meshing domain with the boundary conditions, where the grey lines inside the geometry**
 260 **indicate the different meshing regions; and (b) general view of the computational mesh of the flume, and detail of the**
 261 **model testing zone and the LOWREB dissipative chambers.**

262 The boundary conditions (Figure 3) were defined as follows. The inlet boundary was set to the *waves2Foam*
 263 special wave generating condition both for velocity and volume fraction; pressure and turbulent variables were
 264 set to zero normal gradients. For the atmosphere boundary, a fixed total pressure condition was used; the velocity
 265 was set using a *pressureInletOutletVelocity* condition, which establishes a zero-gradient condition in case of an
 266 outwards flux and calculates the normal velocity on the boundary in the case of an inwards flux; the turbulent
 267 variables and the volume fraction were set to an *inletOutlet* condition allowing water to leave and air to enter the
 268 domain when needed. The bottom, the right wall and the boundaries of the LOWREB caisson were set as fixed
 269 walls with no-slip boundary conditions for velocity, zero gradients for pressure and volume fraction, and wall-
 270 functions for k and ϵ . Finally, given that the computational domain is bi-dimensional, the front and back
 271 boundaries were set to *empty*, i.e., the flow field in the direction perpendicular to these boundaries is not solved.

272 3.3. Testing programme

273 The testing programme involved two different sets of tests. The objective of the first set was to validate the
 274 numerical model. Once validated, the numerical model was used to assess the hydrodynamics of the LOWREB
 275 concept. Finally, a second set of tests was conducted covering additional wave conditions in order to better
 276 understand the behavior of the LOWREB caisson.

277 The validation set reproduces the experimental tests carried out with regular waves. Thus, the wave conditions
 278 considered were those tested in the physical model, obtained as a combination of three wave heights: 0.11, 0.12
 279 and 0.13 m (5.5, 6.0 and 6.5 m in prototype dimensions, respectively); and three wave periods: 1.41, 1.98 and
 280 2.55 s (10, 14 and 18 s in prototype dimensions, respectively). The tests were carried out for two water depths:
 281 low water level (LWL), corresponding to a depth of 0.32 m (16 m in prototype dimensions), and high water level
 282 (HWL), corresponding to a depth of 0.40 m (20 m in prototype dimensions). The majority of the cases were
 283 generated using Stokes theory, choosing between Stokes first-order and Stokes second-order theory depending
 284 on the value of the wave steepness (H/L), being the boundary between linear and Stokes second-order $H/L = 0.04$
 285 (Hedges, 1995). The exception were those cases with a very high Ursell number ($HL^2/d^3 > 50$) in which the
 286 cnoidal theory was used. The total simulation time of every case was 60 s.

287 In the second set of tests the range of studied wave conditions was extended, covering two different situations
 288 corresponding to typical applications of the LOWREB caisson: breakwaters and quay-walls. To test the
 289 hydrodynamic performance of the LOWREB as a low-reflection breakwater, seven regular wave conditions were
 290 considered (Table 1 – conditions 1 to 7). However, port basins are areas protected from the wave action, which
 291 means that in these areas wave conditions are less energetic: in general, waves with shorter periods and smaller
 292 wave heights are observed. Therefore, to assess the behaviour of the LOWREB in inner quay-walls, six
 293 additional less-energetic wave conditions were tested (Table 1 – conditions 8 to 13).

294 **Table 1. Regular wave conditions tested in the second series of numerical model tests.**

Wave condition	Model		Prototype	
	H (m)	T (s)	H (m)	T (s)
1	0.12	1.41	6.0	10
2	0.12	1.70	6.0	12
3	0.12	1.98	6.0	14
4	0.06	1.13	3.0	8
5	0.06	1.41	3.0	10
6	0.06	1.70	3.0	12
7	0.06	1.98	3.0	14
8	0.02	0.57	1.0	4
9	0.02	0.85	1.0	6
10	0.02	1.13	1.0	8
11	0.01	0.57	0.5	4
12	0.01	0.85	0.5	6
13	0.01	1.13	0.5	8

295 The wave conditions of this second set were tested under three different water depths: the LWL and the HWL
 296 mentioned above and, in addition, the mean water level (MWL), corresponding to a depth of 0.36 m (18 m in
 297 prototype dimensions). Thus, a total number of 39 numerical cases were tested. Both the total simulation time
 298 and the criteria for selecting the generation wave theory remain the same of the validation set.

299 Simulations were carried out in the high performance computing (HPC) center at the Faculty of Engineering of
 300 the University of Porto, Portugal (GRID-FEUP). All of them were run in parallel mode with Intel® Xeon® E5-

301 2640 processors at 2.5 GHz, on four computational cores, which reduced the computational time to
302 approximately 24 hours per case for 60 s of simulation.

303 The performance of the LOWREB caisson was evaluated based on the reflection coefficients estimated for every
304 wave condition considered. The reflection analysis was carried out using the two-gauge method of Baldock and
305 Simmonds (1999), which allows separating wave trains propagating over an arbitrary 2D bathymetry and is
306 applicable to both regular and irregular waves.

307 The LOWREB structure, given its geometrical characteristics, may suffer of uplift loads on the horizontal slab at
308 the top (Kisacik *et al.*, 2012a; 2014). Thus, to complement the hydrodynamic analysis of the LOWREB caisson,
309 a preliminary study of the pressure distributions on the horizontal slab was performed. The study of the pressure
310 loads was restricted to the most disadvantageous conditions previously considered, that is, those waves with the
311 higher wave heights (Table 1 – conditions 1 to 3) and under the high water level. To have a high spatial
312 resolution, pressure data was registered at a uniform interval of one data-point each 5 mm. Given the non-
313 repeatability of the breaking wave impact pressures (e.g., Bullock *et al.*, 2007; Kisacik *et al.*, 2012a), pressure
314 measurements were registered for, at least, 10 waves for each test. Data were sampled with a frequency of 1 kHz,
315 a value already used in other studies (e.g., Park *et al.*, 2018).

316 **4. Results**

317 **4.1. Numerical model validation**

318 The comparison between the values of the reflection coefficient obtained from physical and numerical modelling
319 is presented in Figure 4. The agreement between both models, physical and numerical, is quite good, with all the
320 cases but one relatively close to the perfect fit line. Thus, without the mentioned exception, all the cases are
321 within the $\pm 10\%$ lines, which are the limits usually assumed when dealing with reflection coefficients (e.g.,
322 Jacobsen *et al.*, 2015). The numerical model correctly reproduces the three wave periods, both under LWL and
323 HWL. Although the model tends to slightly underestimate the values of the reflection coefficient for the high
324 period waves ($T = 2.55$ s), in general, the points are similarly distributed at both sides of the perfect fit line, i.e.,
325 there is no strong spurious trends introduced by the numerical model. The erroneous point, which corresponds to
326 a high water level wave condition with a period of $T = 1.41$ s, can be considered as an outlier, as its behavior is
327 very different from that of the other two cases of the same period, which present a very good agreement with the
328 experimental values.

329

330

331

Figure 4. Comparison between the values of the reflection coefficient of the physical and numerical tests
(● T = 1.41 s; ★ T = 1.98 s; ◆ T = 2.55; empty symbols: LWL; filled symbols: HWL).

332

Given the nature of the problem and that the great majority of the values of the reflection coefficient obtained from the numerical modelling match those obtained from physical modelling within an acceptable range ($\pm 10\%$), the numerical model can be considered successfully validated.

334

335 4.2. Hydrodynamics of the LOWREB caisson

336

The previous quantitative validation is qualitatively complemented by comparing the hydrodynamic behavior of the LOWREB caisson on both models, physical and numerical. Thus, the interaction between waves and the LOWREB caisson, under a wave condition of $T = 1.41$ s and $H = 0.11$ m, is presented for the physical and numerical models in Figure 5. The snapshots start when the crest of the wave reaches the model and cover an entire wave period.

340

341

It can be seen that the agreement between the two models, although not perfect, is quite good. Below are emphasized some events that show the good matching between both models. First, during the wave run-up, the flow impacts the second and third weirs at snapshots 3 and 4, respectively, both on the physical and numerical model (Figure 5). Second, the run-up flow reaches a similar elevation at the entrance of the LOWREB on both models (snapshots 4 and 5). Third, the slope of the free surface inside the LOWREB during the beginning of the discharge stage is approximately the same on both models (snapshots 8, 9 and 10). Fourth, the curved shape of the free surface over the weirs inside the LOWREB (snapshots 10, 11 and 12) is very well reproduced by the numerical model. Finally, the behavior of the incoming waves, which begin the wave run-up stage by the overtopping of the outflow stream, is also well reproduced by the numerical model (snapshot 14).

349

350

351 **Figure 5. Snapshots of recorded video from the experimental tests and corresponding snapshots from the numerical**
 352 **tests, presenting the wave–LOWREB interaction during an entire wave period under a wave condition of $H = 0.11$ m,**
 353 **$T = 1.41$ s and high water level (the time step is 0.10 s, in model time).**

354 On the downside, the intense flow aeration shown in the physical model at the front of the LOWREB, *e.g.*,
 355 snapshots 12, 13 and 14 (Figure 5), is not perfectly reproduced in the numerical model, which presents larger air
 356 bubbles and lower mixture between air and water phases. This fact can be explained by the 2D nature of the
 357 numerical model and, mainly, by the intrinsic characteristics of the VOF method, which assumes the

358 immiscibility of the phases and makes difficult an accurate prediction of air-entrainment. In any case, the
359 hydrodynamic behavior of the numerical model is, in general, in good agreement with that of the experimental
360 model, complementing and reinforcing the validation process.

361 Additionally, the numerical model enables the assessment of other interesting variables for the study of the
362 hydrodynamics of the LOWREB: the velocity fields (Figure 6), the streamlines (Figure 7) and the vorticity fields
363 (Figure 8). To improve the readability of the figures only the fields of the water phase are represented.

364 The analysis of the velocity fields of the LOWREB caisson (Figure 6) shows an acceleration of the flow near the
365 surface when the waves reach the structure (snapshots 1 and 2). Consequently, wave run-up takes place over the
366 weirs at each dissipative chamber. In the process, the run-up flow also impacts the walls of the chambers and the
367 weirs (snapshots 3 and 4). In this way, the run-up energy is dissipated through turbulence and in the impact with
368 the dissipative chamber contours. The splash of the run-up flow takes place when the wave hits the rear wall of
369 the LOWREB caisson (snapshots 5 and 6). At this point, the particle velocity slows down from around 1.5 m/s
370 (in model scale) during the run-up (snapshots 3 and 4) to about 1.0 m/s after the wave impact on the rear wall of
371 the LOWREB caisson (snapshots 6 and 7). The greater velocities (around 1.8 m/s, in model scale) appear during
372 the discharge stage with the outflow stream generated over the crest of the first weir, at the entrance of the
373 LOWREB structure (snapshot 11).

374 In the run-up stage, two main vortices are formed, as can be seen through the streamlines (Figure 7). The first
375 one appears with the approaching of the wave to the LOWREB caisson, at the front of the structure (snapshots 4
376 and 5). The second vortex is formed inside the first dissipative chamber, behind the first weir, and grows with
377 the wave run-up. Furthermore, in addition to these two vortices, a lot of small vortices are formed inside the
378 dissipative chambers. All these vortices are interesting from the operating point of view of the LOWREB as they
379 contribute to increase the energy dissipation of the structure, so diminishing the wave reflection.

380

381 **Figure 6. Snapshots of the numerical velocity fields during an entire wave period, under a wave condition of $H = 0.11$**
 382 **m , $T = 1.41$ s and high water level (the time step is 0.10 s, in model time).**

383 During the return flow, the streamlines present the characteristic curved shaped of the napped flow (snapshots 9
 384 to 14 in Figure 7). Moreover, recirculating vortices are developed in the spaces between the weirs. Thus, in this
 385 stage, there are two main events in which energy dissipation takes place: first, when water cascades from one
 386 weir to the following one; and second, with the transfer of energy from the outflow stream to the recirculating
 387 vortices formed in the dissipative chambers.

388

389 **Figure 7. Snapshots of the numerical streamlines during an entire wave period, under a wave condition of $H = 0.11$ m,**
 390 **$T = 1.41$ s and high water level (the time step is 0.10 s, in model time).**

391 As regards vorticity (Figure 8), the greatest values appear, all over the entire wave period, in the regions of
 392 contact between the wave flow and the crests of the weirs. The area just at the front of the LOWREB, where the
 393 discharge of the high velocity stream outflow is produced, is another remarkable zone of high vorticity
 394 (snapshots 11 to 14 in Figure 8); here, a large counterclockwise vortex is formed close to the front wall (snapshot
 395 10 in Figure 7 and Figure 8), grows with the increase of the velocity and detaches from the wall at the end of the
 396 wave period (snapshots 12 to 14). Considering the sign of the vorticity, it can be seen that the run-up stage is
 397 dominated by negative values, i.e., clockwise rotation (bluish colors of snapshots 1 to 7 in Figure 8), whereas the
 398 return flow stage is dominated by positive values, i.e., counterclockwise rotation (yellowish colors of snapshots
 399 8 to 14 in Figure 8).

400

401 **Figure 8. Snapshots of the numerical vorticity fields (component orthogonal to the plane of motion) during an entire**
 402 **wave period, under a wave condition of $H = 0.11$ m, $T = 1.41$ s and high water level (the time step is 0.10 s, in model**
 403 **time).**

404 **4.3. Performance under extended wave conditions**

405 The analysis of the efficiency of the LOWREB caisson with respect to wave reflection for the extended range of
 406 wave conditions tested with the numerical model is presented in Figure 9. The left side of each graph (smaller
 407 periods and less-energetic waves) corresponds to the assessment of the LOWREB behavior in inner quay-walls;
 408 the right side corresponds to the assessment of the LOWREB as a low-reflection breakwater. It should be noted
 409 that the aim of the LOWREB is to reduce the wave reflection; therefore, the lower the reflection coefficient, the
 410 better the performance of the LOWREB.

411

412 **Figure 9. Values of the reflection coefficient (C_R) for the different wave conditions tested in the numerical model. Each**
 413 **graph corresponds to a different water level: low water level (LWL), mean water level (MWL) and high water level**
 414 **(HWL).**

415 Comparing the three graphs in Figure 9, the influence of the water level on the reflection coefficient is evident;
 416 thus, there are differences from up to 80 percentage points in the values of the reflection coefficient between low
 417 and high water levels for the same wave condition (e.g., $H = 0.06$ m, $T = 1.41$ s). Overall, the LOWREB
 418 achieves the best performance for the high water level condition, for which the values of the reflection
 419 coefficient for the great majority of the wave conditions are well below 60%. The performance of the LOWREB
 420 for the mean water level is also satisfactory, with all the values of the reflection coefficient below 70% and most
 421 of them in the range 30%–60%. At low water level, the performance of the LOWREB is not good: all the values
 422 of the reflection coefficient are above 70%. Therefore, the geometry of the LOWREB caisson is not optimized
 423 for the low water level. The strong influence of the water level on the LOWREB performance must be related to
 424 the accessibility of the wave to the LOWREB dissipative chambers, which is more difficult under the low water
 425 level. In fact, in this situation waves hardly overtop the weir of the third dissipative chamber (the higher one). A
 426 similar conclusion was found in the experimental model tests (Ciocan *et al.*, 2017).

427 Paying attention to the graph of the low water level (Figure 9 – LWL), the values of the reflection coefficient for
 428 the two smaller wave heights ($H = 0.01$ and 0.02 m) are near 100%, *i.e.*, the LOWREB performs as a vertical
 429 wall. The reason is that the waves are not able to overtop even the first weir (*e.g.*, Figure 10). When the wave
 430 height increases, the LOWREB starts to perform better. In fact, for this water level, the wave height is the
 431 variable that most influence the reflection coefficient: the higher the wave height, the lower the reflection
 432 coefficient. The influence of the wave period is comparatively smaller.

433
 434 **Figure 10. Snapshots from the numerical tests, presenting the wave–LOWREB interaction during an entire wave period**
 435 **under a wave condition of $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.57$ s and low water level (the time step is 0.10 s, in model time).**

436 A different situation takes place for the high water level condition (Figure 9 – HWL). For HWL, wave period is
 437 clearly the most important variable on the LOWREB performance. For a given wave height, variations in the
 438 wave period produce changes in the values of the reflection coefficient of more than 20 percentage points.
 439 Particularly interesting are the results of $H = 0.06$ m: there is a wave period ($T = 1.41$ s) for which the energy
 440 dissipation is maximum ($C_R \approx 10\%$). What is more, the LOWREB improves its performance (lower values of the
 441 reflection coefficient) when the wave period gets close to this optimum period for the four studied wave heights.
 442 This behavior, however, is not reproduced for the mean water level condition (Figure 9 – MWL): there is no
 443 optimum period, at least, in the range of studied wave conditions. Therefore, the performance of the LOWREB is
 444 highly influenced by the combined effect of wave period and water level.

445 With the aim of confirming the exceptional performance achieved by the LOWREB at high water level for a
 446 wave condition of $H = 0.06$ m and $T = 1.41$ s, two additional cases were tested, maintaining the wave height and
 447 introducing small variations in the wave period ($T = 1.30$ and 1.50 s). The values of the reflection coefficient for
 448 this additional wave conditions are presented in red in Figure 9 – HWL. The performance of the LOWREB is in
 449 accordance with the previous results. Thus, a well-defined trend towards an optimum period in the vicinity of
 450 $T = 1.30$ - 1.41 s can be observed. Similar values of the reflection coefficient (about 10%) were also found for
 451 optimum conditions in other low-reflection structures (*e.g.*, Faraci *et al.*, 2014).

452 Special attention must be paid to the low-energy wave conditions. For the MWL, the values of the reflection
 453 coefficient increase when the wave period increases. Nevertheless, for the HWL, the values of the reflection

454 coefficient decrease when wave period increases. At MWL, the low-energy waves are not able to overtop the
 455 crest of the second weir, so only one of the three dissipative chambers of the LOWREB is effectively working.
 456 At HWL, the low-energy waves do overtop the crest of the second weir and two dissipative chambers work. This
 457 situation improves the performance of the LOWREB for the wave period of $T = 1.13$ s and worsen it for $T = 0.57$
 458 s; for an intermediate period ($T = 0.85$ s) the performance of the LOWREB is the same for both water levels.
 459 Again, it is shown that the LOWREB efficiency is highly influenced by the combined effect of wave period and
 460 water level.

461 As regards wave height, in general, the reflection coefficient decreases when the wave height increases. This is
 462 true for low and mean water levels, and for the less-energetic wave conditions of the high water level. However,
 463 at high water level this trend switches under the more-energetic wave conditions ($H = 0.06$ and 0.12 m); in this
 464 case, the highest wave height corresponds to the lowest performance of the LOWREB. In this situation,
 465 probably, the total height of the LOWREB structure is not enough to correctly dissipate the incident wave
 466 energy; in fact, for the high water level, the largest waves are close to overtop the structure (*e.g.*, Figure 5).

467 To better characterize the behavior of the LOWREB, the values of the reflection coefficient are presented versus
 468 the relative crest freeboard, $R^* = Y/(H+h)$, in Figure 11, for the entire set of tested wave conditions. This non-
 469 dimensional parameter is usually defined as the ratio of the height of the structure over the water level (*i.e.*, the
 470 crest freeboard) to the wave height; however, in this case, to prevent the numerator from being equal to zero, the
 471 water depth was added in the denominator rather than subtracted from the chamber height (see Figure 2 for
 472 definition of the chamber height, Y). Following the subdivision established in Section 3.3, the dataset was
 473 divided into high-energetic waves (Table 1 – conditions 1 to 7) and low-energetic waves (Table 1 – conditions 8
 474 to 13). In general, the lower the relative crest freeboard, the lower the values of the reflection coefficient. This
 475 shows that in order to reduce the values of the reflection coefficient, the crest freeboard should be smaller than
 476 the wave height, which is directly related to the capability of the waves to overtop the weirs and reach the
 477 dissipative chambers. The slope of the fitted line is greater for the low-energetic waves, which means that the
 478 influence of the relative crest freeboard on the performance of the LOWREB is higher under these conditions
 479 characterized by smaller wave heights. An appropriate design of the LOWREB should ensure values of the
 480 relative crest freeboard never greater than one and, preferably, below 0.9 for low-energetic waves and 0.8
 481 for high-energetic waves.

482

483

Figure 11. Values of the reflection coefficient (C_R) as a function of the relative crest freeboard (R^*).

484 Other non-dimensional parameters usually employed in the study of conventional non-reflective structures, *e.g.*,
 485 the relative dissipation chamber width (ratio of the chamber width to the wavelength), are hardly applicable to
 486 the LOWREB concept due to the presence of the inner weirs and the variable water depths inside the dissipative
 487 chambers, which modify the effective dissipation chamber width, making the analysis highly complex. Thus,
 488 although the performance of the LOWREB is highly influenced by the wave period, no non-dimensional
 489 parameter was found which related this influence to any other of the investigated variables in a clear manner.

490 4.4. Pressures on the horizontal slab

491 The time-varying spatial pressure distributions for one of the tested cases are presented in Figure 12, in which
 492 the normalized time (t/T) is represented along the y -axis, the x -axis shows the normalized position along the
 493 horizontal slab at the top of the LOWREB structure (x/x_L), and the normalized pressure is represented in the
 494 z -axis. For readability, only three consecutive wave impacts are presented. It can be seen that the impact
 495 behavior varies from one wave to another, as initially expected. The higher pressures are located on the first half
 496 of the slab, with the maximum pressure at the corner near the vertical wall. Further away from the first half of
 497 the slab, pressure diminish substantially.

498 **Figure 12. Time-varying spatial pressure profiles on the horizontal slab for three consecutive wave impacts, under a**
 499 **wave condition of $H = 0.12$ m, $T = 1.98$ s and for the high water level.**
 500

501 To better analyze the most disadvantageous conditions, the normalized instantaneous pressure profiles at the
 502 time of maximum pressures are presented in Figure 13, for the three considered cases (Table 1 – conditions 1 to
 503 3). The pressure profiles of the three conditions are similar: a near-triangular shape with the maximum pressure
 504 at the corner of the structure, reducing progressively towards the tip of the horizontal slab. However, the
 505 differences both in magnitude and in affected length of the slab are noticeable. Thus, for the two smaller periods,
 506 $T = 1.41$ and 1.70 s (Figure 13 – A and B), the wave impact is located in the first fifth of the horizontal slab
 507 ($0 < x/x_L < 0.2$). For the larger period, $T = 1.98$ s (Figure 13 – C), the wave impact affects, approximately, four
 508 fifths of the total length of the slab ($0 < x/x_L < 0.8$). This larger period is also that which presents the higher
 509 values of the reflection coefficient of the three here evaluated (Figure 9 – HWL). This indicates that the higher

510 pressures take place for wave conditions with the higher reflections, i.e., those for which the hydraulic efficiency
 511 of the LOWREB is low. In any case, the values of the maximum pressure are not very high, $p_{max} < 3\rho gH$. In
 512 previous studies dealing with wave impacts on vertical structures with horizontal slabs, values of the maximum
 513 pressure well above $50\rho gH$ were found (Kisacik *et al.*, 2012a; 2012b). The particular geometrical shape of the
 514 LOWREB, which forces wave breaking and enhances energy dissipation, is surely related to these comparatively
 515 lower pressures. This is a good result, in the sense that the integrity of the caisson seems not to be particularly
 516 threatened because of the wave impacts, nor operating as a breakwater nor consequently as a quay-wall.

517
 518 **Figure 13. Normalized instantaneous pressure profiles at the time of maximum pressures: (A) $H = 0.12$ m, $T = 1.41$ s; (B)**
 519 **$H = 0.12$ m, $T = 1.70$ s; and (C) $H = 0.12$ m, $T = 1.98$ s.**

520 Finally, it should be noted that this pressure analysis is preliminary and despite showing a general representation
 521 of the behavior of the structure when facing wave impacts, demands a cautious evaluation of the results. In fact,
 522 an in-depth study of the problem requires the improvement of some points, e.g., a higher sampling frequency and
 523 a higher number of analyzed waves for reducing the uncertainty associated with non-repeatability. Furthermore,
 524 a comparison with experimental pressure measurements would be recommended to confirm the numerical model
 525 results. This is a topic that deserves further study.

526 5. Conclusions

527 In this work, the OpenFOAM® CFD package in combination with the *waves2Foam* wave generation toolbox
 528 was used to implement a RANS-VOF numerical model of the LOWREB concept. The model, once validated
 529 using the results from experimental tests, was applied, first, to carry out an in-depth study of the hydrodynamics
 530 of the LOWREB and, second, to assess its performance under an extended range of wave conditions, covering in
 531 this way the main uses of the LOWREB caisson concept: external caisson breakwater or inner low reflective
 532 quay-wall.

533 The validation was carried out following a two-stage approach. First, the values of the reflection coefficient
534 calculated from the numerical model simulations were compared with those from experimental modelling. A
535 good agreement was found: excepting one outlier, all the cases are within the $\pm 10\%$ error interval. After that, a
536 qualitative validation was made by comparing the wave-structure interaction on both models, physical and
537 numerical, under a given wave condition. A series of characteristic events were analyzed, showing a good
538 matching between the physical and numerical models.

539 The analysis of the LOWREB hydrodynamics, for which the velocity fields, the streamlines and the vorticity
540 fields were evaluated, enabled the detailed characterization of the energy dissipation events that take place in the
541 wave-LOWREB interaction. These are, mainly, the impacts of the wave run-up flow with the weirs of the
542 dissipative chambers during the wave run-up stage, and the napped flow (the outflow stream that cascades from
543 one weir to another) during the spill-out stage. These events contribute to the formation of numerous vortices
544 along the entire wave period cycle, not only inside the dissipative chambers but also in front of the LOWREB
545 structure. All these mechanisms increase turbulence and, in this way, energy dissipation through viscous shear
546 stress.

547 The performance of the LOWREB, characterized based on the values of the reflection coefficient, was found to
548 be highly influenced by the combined effect of wave period and water level. The influence of the wave height
549 although comparatively lower, is not negligible; in general, a higher wave height contributes to improve the
550 energy dissipation. Overall, the LOWREB achieves its best performance for the high water level condition, with
551 all the values of the reflection coefficient below 70% and most of them in the range 30%-60%. In this situation,
552 the existence of an optimum period ($1.13 \text{ s} < T_{opt} < 1.50 \text{ s}$) which maximizes the energy dissipation of the device
553 (a minimum $C_R \approx 10\%$ was obtained for $H = 0.06 \text{ m}$) was proven. Although this fact suggests that there could be
554 an optimum wave period for a given wave height such that the energy dissipation is maximum, this optimum
555 period was only found at the high water level, so further investigations must be done in this direction. The
556 performance for the mean water level was also good ($30\% < C_R < 70\%$), in particular, for the less-energetic wave
557 conditions of shorter period, under which the LOWREB improves the performance achieved at high water level.
558 On the contrary, the performance at low water level was found to be poor for the entire range of wave conditions
559 ($C_R > 70\%$). It is associated with the difficulties that waves have, at this water level, to overtop the weirs and
560 enter the dissipative chambers. To overcome this situation, the LOWREB must be designed to have a relative
561 crest freeboard (R^*) below one. Finally, the analysis of the pressure distributions on the horizontal slab of the
562 LOWREB showed that the integrity of the device is not particularly threatened because of the wave impacts.

563 To sum up, in this work the hydrodynamic performance of the LOWREB caisson was successfully assessed by
564 means of a RANS-VOF numerical model. The results were promising, with values of the reflection coefficient
565 below 70% for the entire range of wave conditions tested at mean and high water levels. Therefore, the
566 LOWREB concept was shown to be an appropriate low-reflection solution both for breakwaters and quay-walls.
567 Future work should include the development of geometry modifications to ensure a better performance of the
568 LOWREB caisson at lower water levels.

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